

ANALYSIS OF WATER CONSUMPTION REQUIRED FOR INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES OF FERGANA CITY.

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ABSTRAKT. The article examines the issues of discharge, treatment and quantity determination of waste water produced in industrial enterprises. The analysis of these indicators is considered in the case of Fergana city.

KEYWORDS: industrial wastewater; cleaning methods; determine the amount of water.

INTRODUCTION. Discharge and treatment of waste water generated in industrial enterprises, composition and properties of waste water, treatment of waste water, methods of treatment of retained waste and treatment of treated water, types of constructions used, their structure and methodology of their calculation, as well as the results of socio-economic reforms in our republic and regional problems issues of influence on the perspective of the wastewater treatment system are one of the most urgent issues of today.

Rapid development of industrial enterprises is one of the factors of pollution of water bodies. While discharging large amounts of wastewater into water bodies, maintaining their purity is one of the important tasks in the municipal economy. Therefore, with the correct selection of industrial wastewater treatment methods, it is possible to ensure that the water discharged into water bodies fully complies with sanitary standards.

The main part. In industrial enterprises, technical water is used in three directions:

1. From 70 to 89% of the incoming water for technical purposes is used in industrial enterprises as a refrigerant for cooling the products of heat exchange equipment, or to keep individual elements of devices and machines from overheating This water is heated by the product being cooled, but is not contaminated.

2. The amount of technical water from 5 to 12% is used for cleaning products or raw materials and as a transportation medium. This water becomes contaminated and heats up if the product is at a high temperature.

3. From 10 to 20% of technical water is lost due to evaporation or enters the composition of the manufactured product (steam, sugar, bread, etc.)

Due to economic considerations, environmental requirements, as well as the limitation of water reserves in natural sources, it is recommended to install a circulation system of technical water supply in industrial enterprises. In the circulating system of technical water supply, water is used many times.

According to the change in water quality during operation, circulating water supply is divided into the following:

1. "Clean cycles" - only for hot water when used;
2. "Dirty cycles" - when used only for polluted water;
3. "Mixed cycles" - when used, water is heated and polluted at the same time.

Limit for technical water used in industrial enterprises of group 1 the temperature is determined. T should be $<30^{\circ}\text{C}$, its optimal value should be 15°C .

In circulating water supply systems, carbonate hardness of water used as Ca and Mg carriers (chlorides) should not exceed $J_k - 2.8 \dots 3.0 \text{ mg-eq/l}$, and the possible concentration of its weight, according to the speed of water movement in cooling devices, is accepted.

The technical water demand of the enterprise depends on the type of equipment used and the accepted scheme of the technological process. Q_r is determined only according to the technical data of the water-consuming equipment.

In the literature [10-12], information is provided on the limit norms of water consumption per unit of product (per unit of finished product weight). These data are obtained from the result of processing and determining the average amount of water consumption values (in one or another industry). But these standards do not fully take into account the peculiarities of each specific enterprise and can only be used for approximate calculations.

It is considered appropriate to use the water used for the area of the water intake facility for circulating water supply. Recirculating schemes open up great opportunities in reducing the cost of the water supply system, reducing the consumption of fresh water and the discharge of dirty water. When creating circulation circuits, only 70-85% of technical water in technological equipment is used, after heating and cooling, the state of reuse. In these systems, it is possible to use some part of relatively less polluted technical water. Treated water (15%) is reused. In the circulation system of water supply, pumps deliver water to consumers through the water supply network.

The heated and contaminated water from the consumers is directed to the wastewater treatment station through the pipeline system. Purified, but still

warm, water is collected in a reservoir, from which it is transferred to a cooling unit with circulating water station pumps [4].

In it, the cooled water is again delivered to consumers by pumps. During the operation of the circulating system, part of the water is lost: it leaks, evaporates and flies away from the cooling device; runoff and consumer contaminated, non-reusable water can be lost due to discharge into the drains. To make up for these losses, a suitable amount of water is taken from the natural source and directed to the water treatment stations through pumps. Purified water is discharged into the reservoir of cooling devices. Part of the water from the reservoir is continuously discharged into the sewer to maintain the salt balance [2,3,4].

Circulating systems are built according to technical conditions, environmental requirements and economic considerations [2,4].

According to technical conditions, it is necessary to use this system, because the discharge of the existing natural water source is not enough for direct water supply. The need for circulation systems is also explained by environmental requirements. When using circulation systems, the amount of dirty water entering the water bodies is reduced. From an ecological point of view, leak-free circulation systems have great value. Instead of clean water in non-flow (closed) water supply systems in enterprises, biologically purified water is used in advance, purified to the standard of technical water quality of industrial and domestic wastewater [4].

Biologically treated wastewater used in technical water supply must meet technical, economic and sanitary-hygienic requirements. Even if it meets the appropriate standards, it is not possible to use such water in the food, meat, dairy and pharmaceutical industries [3].

According to economic considerations, when using circulating water supply systems, it is possible to reduce costs for the construction of cyv collection devices, first treatment pumping stations, natural and wastewater treatment facilities [4].

The enterprise's water needs of all categories are met from natural sources that meet the following basic requirements:

- a) to ensure the continuous supply of the necessary amount of water for the future development of the enterprise;
- b) delivery of water of a quality that more fully meets the needs of consumers or is achieved due to simple and ecological treatment of the initial water;

c) provides the possibility of supplying water to consumers with low consumption of means;

g) should have such a capacity that taking water from it should not disturb the existing ecological system.

Correctly solving the issue of choosing a source of water supply for a specific consumer requires careful study and analysis of water resources in the area where the consumer is located. Surface and underground waters are used for water supply of industrial enterprises. Surface sources are rivers, lakes, reservoirs; underground sources are groundwater and artesian waters and springs [6].

The water of many rivers has a significant turbidity, a high content of organic substances and bacteria, and often a significant color. At the same time, water is characterized by relatively less hardness [6].

Lake water is usually distinguished by a very small amount of suspended matter (ie, low turbidity). The quality of all ground water is intrinsically dependent on atmospheric precipitation and snowmelt. During floods, their turbidity and bacterial contamination increase, and their hardness decreases.

Artesian waters, as a rule, do not contain suspended matter (that is, very transparent), have low bacterial contamination, but along with these positive qualities, in most cases, they are strongly mineralized. According to the nature of dissolved salts in them, they can have one or another negative properties: high hardness, unpleasant taste and some other properties [6].

The issue of choosing a source of water supply is one of the main issues in the design of drinking water supply facilities, because it determines the presence of one or another facility, and therefore the cost of construction and operation [4].

When choosing a source of water supply, it is necessary to take into account the quality of water and its capacity. The choice of water source is mainly determined by local natural conditions, so first topographical, hydrological, sanitary and other studies are carried out [6].

It is recommended to use underground water sources for household - drinking water supply, and their non-use requires comprehensive reasons. ShNQ 2.04.02-2019 prohibits the use of underground water for drinking quality for purposes not related to domestic drinking water supply [4].

When there are several water sources, the available options are compared technically and economically. Water collection facilities are built to

take water from a natural source and partially purify it. Source selection should be carried out according to UzDSt 951-2011 [6].

Fergana city industrial enterprises have an average of 10 accidents a year, and 0.20% of the annual amount of drinking water is used for this. An average of 12 accidents occur in the city of Margilan in a year, and 0.17% of the annual amount of drinking water is used for this. On average, accidents occur 12 times a year in the city of Kukan, and 0.24% of the annual amount of drinking water is used for this. In the city of Kuvasoy, on average, 20 accidents occur in a year, and 0.91% of the annual amount of drinking water is used for this [9]. Taking into account the above information, it will be possible to prevent industrial enterprises from throwing large amounts of wastewater into water bodies without treatment by analyzing water consumption.

CONCLUSIONS According to economic considerations, it is possible to reduce costs for the construction of cyv collection devices, primary treatment stations, natural and wastewater treatment facilities when using circulating water supply systems. With the correct selection of industrial wastewater treatment methods, it is possible to ensure that the water discharged into water bodies fully complies with sanitary standards. Due to the prevention of pollution of water bodies with industrial wastewater, the level of environmental safety will be increased.

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